

Valuation of nature-based solutions: Methods, challenges and critical considerations

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ABSTRACT

This paper explores the valuation of Nature-based Solutions (NbS) and the critical considerations involved in their economic assessment. NbS leverage ecosystems to achieve goals such as biodiversity protection, with applications ranging from urban green spaces to large-scale forest conservation. This paper discusses the social and economic value of ecosystem services provided by NbS. Economic methods for valuing biodiversity, including Revealed Preference, Stated Preference, and Production Function methods, are examined, highlighting their critical aspects and the importance of integrating non-market values into policy decisions.

1. Introduction

Biodiversity spans genes, species, and ecosystems, providing benefits such as food, medicine, recreation, and cultural identity. Biodiversity is, however, rapidly declining impacting ecosystem services and human well-being. It is threatened by habitat loss, overexploitation, invasive species, climate change, and pollution, all caused by human behaviour [42,68]. Policies are thus needed to protect and restore biodiversity. Policy design depends on the societal values biodiversity creates, and the values associated with biodiversity losses. The Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 [33] and the Water Framework Directive (European Commission, Directive 2000/60/EC [34]) set the agenda, but policies can also more specifically include tools like offsetting and putting requirements on investors to compensate for biodiversity loss [8,57], subsidies, taxes, and fees [64], and Payment for Ecosystem Services [87].

Nature-based solutions (NbS) protect, manage, or restore ecosystems and biodiversity [75]. The contexts vary immensely, from urban green spaces to wetland restoration, and the scale can range from small, such as green roofs, to large, such as forest conservation or marine protection. In this paper, we provide an overview of how ecosystems provide various ecosystem services to humans, and how NbS and biodiversity affect these services.

We focus on the economic value of these services. The standard approach measuring value in economics is observing market behaviour and inferring value from market transactions. Most studies in economics value specific items of natural capital like ecosystems, species, and resources [26]. However, in many instances there are no markets for

biodiversity or ecosystem services. It has therefore been necessary to develop other methods to be able to measure these non-market values. And not including all values in a valuation of an environmental good or a resource can lead to serious undervaluation of that good or resource.

In the following sections, we review the three prominent economic methods for valuing non-market values of biodiversity and ecosystem services: Revealed Preference (RP) methods, Stated Preference (SP) methods, and the Production Function (PF) method. Although the methods are well-known and extensively used, we believe it is important to review the fundamental properties and how these are linked to our analytical framework. Our main interest lies in the actual application of the methods. We begin this with a meta-analysis on scientific valuation studies of NbS in Europe. The main purpose of this literature review is to provide an overview of what methods have been used to estimate what kinds of different values, what types of environments have been investigated (marine, forest, urban etc.), as well as what kinds of NbS (manage, protect, or restore) have previously been investigated. This links the valuation methods to their actual application, showing what methods have been used to assess which types of values and nature-based solutions. We then provide a critical appraisal of the strengths and weaknesses inherent in each method. This draws on the broader valuation literature, but we focus on the valuation of biodiversity and NbS. We then discuss what makes biodiversity particularly challenging to value, what the implications are, but also how to address these challenges.

The paper is structured as follows. First, we explore the values of biodiversity from an anthropocentric view, linking these values to

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ecosystem services, and discuss the role of NbS in an analytical framework. We then present the main economic methods used to assess the social value of biodiversity, followed by our meta-analysis on scientific valuation studies of NbS in Europe. Finally, we discuss the critical aspects of each of these methods, the particular aspects of biodiversity that are important for valuation and the implications for the provision and funding of NbS.

2. Analytical framework

NbS protects, restores, and manages ecosystems to protect biodiversity. To understand the role of NbS, it is therefore necessary to connect it to the values that biodiversity provides to society. Our focus is on an anthropocentric view, emphasising human values and the utility we obtain from biodiversity and ecosystems. We start by describing four different types of values for humans that ecosystems provide. These are: direct and indirect use values, non-use values, and option values.

Direct use values: This is primarily the output from the ecosystem that is consumed directly, like food, but also amenity values from recreation and ecotourism, where biodiversity is a source of enjoyment for humans. The use value also includes productive use-values, i.e. goods

that are inputs and are transformed in a production process, like paper, wood, and silk.

Indirect use values: Values from biodiversity that support human well-being without direct use. Examples are the regulating and maintaining services the ecosystems provide to reduce pollution, and climate regulation. These also include human existence values, i.e. that biodiversity loss can threaten human lives by causing pollution, landslides, or storms, and harm human health values by e.g. decreased protection from pandemics [26].

Non-use values: One important type is existence values: that humans care about the existence of the ecosystems [26]. They are not dependent on the ecosystem’s services. Instead, humans benefit from simply knowing that ecosystems are protected and restored. This can concern whole ecosystems, but also specific endangered species. Another type is warm-glow values [1] linked to the value of supporting the ecosystem through for example donations. Two other values are bequest value – the value of preserving for future generations – and altruistic values – the value that biodiversity is available for others in the current generation.

Option values: This is a value for possible future use, because it might provide benefits in the future that are unknown to us today. One

Fig. 1. Ecosystem services and NbS.

Note: We use a traffic-light system to show how much users depend on the services: black means strong dependence, dark grey means dependence, and light grey means little reliance.

example is an option for future recreational use of, e.g. national parks. Another example is that the loss of diversity in animals and plants, including genetic diversity, poses a serious risk to global food security by undermining the resilience of many agricultural systems to threats such as pests and climate change [42].

Use values are enjoyed foremost by the local population, in particular regarding provisioning services, while non-use values can easily extend to a broader set of people and ultimately be of global concern.

The Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services defines three broad categories of ecosystem services: provisioning services, regulating and maintenance services, and cultural services. In Fig. 1, we illustrate the different aspects of ecosystems' value to humans, but we also introduce Nature-based solutions that manage, restore, and protect ecosystems, while at the same time benefiting people through ecosystem services. Note that supporting services, such as climate regulation, are foundational processes enabling other services and are thus not separately classified in this framework.

Many of the aspects of the values, in particular the indirect-use and non-use values, are primarily non-market values that typically are not bought or sold in the market, while for several of the direct use-values, markets could be in place. This implies that policies are needed to make the right amount of investment in biodiversity, as markets do not always include information about all the values. As indirect-use and non-use values are not revealed in the market, economists have developed non-market valuation methods to provide estimates that can be used in a decision-making framework such as a cost-benefit analysis (CBA). Not including these values in a CBA might severely underestimate the total value of biodiversity.

Note that we do not include any intrinsic value of ecosystems, i.e., values of biodiversity independent of how humans value it and beyond the instrumental value it provides to humans [26]. While we acknowledge that such values could be important, we focus specifically on human well-being. This reflects an ethical choice commonly made in economics: to apply a consequentialist and anthropocentric ethical view. Concerns about non-human species will be included if they are concerns of human well-being. Numerous studies find that humans do put a value on animal welfare (see e.g., [16,23]). We recognise that this choice is not obvious and may be subject to debate, and that there are other normative possibilities with a focus on the rights of non-human species [78], or the view that certain natural assets are non-substitutable, which would conflict with designing policy based on people's preferences and trade-offs between natural and human-made capital.

Furthermore, the framework does not directly account for distributional outcomes [59]. However, it is straightforward to illustrate whose values one is measuring, as illustrated in Fig. 1. In many cases, an analysis of the socio-economic impacts of NbS provides important information for policy design. For example, Ecosystem restoration usually presents net benefits for the entire society, but it can cause net losses for specific social groups, possibly also for vulnerable populations [14,79].

NbS benefit citizens through e.g., improved health and consumption of goods, and firms through for example, ecosystem services used for their production and climate regulation. We also distinguish between local, regional, and global actors. There is often a difference in what services that, for example, local and global firms would derive benefits from, and the exact service depends on the type of ecosystem. Furthermore, firms would mostly rely on direct-use values from ecosystems. The provisioning services primarily benefit individuals who are close to the NbS, while in this global economy, the direct use of provisioning services could benefit firms that are located far from the NbS. The indirect use values of provisioning and regulation services are primarily of value for local citizens and firms. The global concern about NbS primarily relates to non-use values such as the existence value or option values.

3. Methods

We conduct a literature review on valuation studies; valuing biodiversity and NbS. We review which valuation methods have been applied across environments (marine, forest, urban etc.), and nature-based solution strategies (manage, protect, or restore). We limit our attention to studies done in Europe. Given the development of EU policies, in particular the EU taxonomy for sustainable investments, Europe is a case where there is a growing interest in investing and evaluating NbS. The main purpose of the literature review is to provide an overview of what methods are used and what types of environments and NbS have been investigated. The focus is on published academic work. The literature search used public databases (EVRI, ENVALUE), Google Scholar, Scopus, and cross-references from primary articles. Inclusion criteria covered all types of English-language primary published studies focusing on valuation of nature-based solutions and biodiversity by European citizens. The keywords are: value OR valuation OR "economic value" OR "economic benefit*" OR "willingness to pay" OR wtp OR preference* OR "stated preference" OR "contingent valuation" OR "dichotomous choice" OR "choice experiment" OR "stated choice" OR "travel cost*" OR "hedonic pricing" OR "market price*" AND biodiversity. From the resulting list, we identified studies conducted in Europe, especially those involving geographically specific nature-based solutions. Before we look at the results, we will discuss the economic valuation methods, with a particular focus on valuing NbS as well as the critical aspects of each of the methods. We will link the methods with the types of values that they are able to estimate. The total number of articles included with these search words was 58, 16 studies were excluded because they did not fulfil the definition of an NbS, and the final number of articles included in the review is 42.

4. An overview of economic approaches for measuring values

The two main measures of economic values are Willingness to Pay (WTP) and Willingness to Accept compensation (WTA). Consider two biodiversity levels: poor and good. Since individuals are better off with good biodiversity, their utility is higher. WTP is the maximum amount an individual would pay so that utility with good biodiversity equals that with poor biodiversity—i.e., the money they give up to gain the improvement. WTA is the minimum amount they require so that utility with poor biodiversity equals that with good biodiversity. WTP is more commonly used than WTA, primarily because most methods rely on studying behaviour in markets, where consumers' WTP are revealed.

4.1. Revealed preferences

Revealed Preference (RP) methods infer values from people's behaviour in existing related markets. This is possible when the level of the public good (e.g., water quality) affects the value of the private good (e.g., a trip to a beach). Two commonly used RP methods are the Travel Cost method and the Hedonic Price method.¹

4.1.1. Travel cost

The travel cost method (TCM) measures WTP for goods such as national parks and other recreational areas. Individuals spend money and time to visit parks, and these expenditures can be seen as the price they pay for visiting the park [41].

The method uses the fact that different individuals have different costs to travel to the same place, allowing estimation of a demand function for visits. A TCM study collects data on travel costs and the number of visits to the recreational site. The target population is visitors

¹ A third approach is the defensive expenditure method, which estimates the cost of avoiding environmental harm by assuming people act when benefits outweigh costs [2,30].

to the site, and the focus is on the direct use value of the site, usually the recreational value. A demand function describing the relationship between cost and the number of visits. This facilitates measurement of the total value that individuals derive from visiting the site, representing the welfare beyond the incurred costs. There are several types of travel cost models (TCM). The earliest and simplest is the zonal TCM, where visitors are grouped by distance (e.g., city or postal code) and assumed to face the same travel cost [25], making it the least data-intensive. The individual TCM uses data on each visitor's travel costs, requiring more details [13]. The most data-intensive is the Random Utility Model, which analyses choices among multiple sites and can estimate the value of site-specific characteristics [50]. For example, it can show how much more people would pay to visit a site rich in biodiversity compared to a poor one.

4.1.2. Hedonic pricing

HPM explains variations in house prices based on differences in house characteristics, including environmental attributes. Examples of HPM studies include studies about air quality, forests, proximity to parks, and neighbourhood safety on house prices [22,70,80]. These environmental attributes are not directly traded in markets, but they are aspects of a house's location and therefore bundled with the market value of a house.

The hedonic theory of equilibrium in markets for differentiated products was developed by Rosen [72]. The value of a house depends on the bundle of attributes that characterize the house. The hedonic price function specifies how the market prices of the product vary as the attributes vary. The hedonic price function $p(z)$ reflects an equilibrium, with each point determined by supply and demand for the characteristics in vector z . Controlling for other attributes, the price difference between two identical houses—except one having an extra bedroom—represents the value of that bedroom. The same logic applies to non-market goods like air quality. Note that the hedonic price function shows the overall price based on the combination of characteristics, and this is not the marginal valuation for a certain characteristic. Taking the slope of the hedonic price function reflects the marginal valuation. The literature has outlined a two-step procedure; step 1 is to estimate the hedonic price function. It is not obvious which functional form to use, but it must be determined from what best fits the data [66,72]. In the second step, the inverse demand function is estimated. To do this the marginal valuation (the slope and the partial derivative) of the hedonic price function is computed and evaluated at the sample values of the vector z , and the resulting variables are used as the dependent variables. The main independent variable is the quantity/quality of the environmental attribute, together with the socio-economic characteristics of the households. The area under the estimated demand curve reflects individual welfare from the quantity or quality of the environmental attribute

4.2. Stated preferences

SP methods are used to estimate values of non-market goods and changes in existing goods. In surveys, individuals state their preferences hypothetically—by reporting maximum WTP, minimum WTA, or choosing among alternatives—without real money transactions.

Two widely used SP methods are: the contingent valuation (CV) and the choice experiment (CE) method. Both methods measure preferences for public goods through surveys. Survey design—sampling, mode (postal, in-person, online), and socio-economic questions—is often similar for CV and CE.

CV values a bundle of attributes together, while CE values individual attributes. Both methods usually value changes from a baseline, e.g., an improvement in biodiversity from the status quo. Alternatively, it concerns avoiding deterioration of environmental quality from the current baseline.

The scenario is an important part of the survey; it describes the good,

its current situation, what the improvement will be, and when and how it will be achieved. A payment vehicle should be realistic, credible, familiar, and binding for all respondents [46]. Non-binding payment vehicles, like donations, are not incentive compatible, while mandatory payments are, and they can also prevent free riding.² To increase the validity, respondents are often reminded of substitute goods, and they are given a “budget reminder”.

4.2.1. Contingent valuation

In CV respondents state their maximum WTP for a defined scenario, such as improving biodiversity (see e.g. [24,77,102]). Response formats include open-ended, closed-ended, and payment cards. In the open-ended format, respondents state WTP directly, but it is prone to strategic bias [21]. In the closed-ended format, respondents accept or reject a randomized bid; it resembles a market transaction and is less sensitive to bias, but requires larger samples. The payment card format offers multiple bids, and respondents choose the closest to their true WTP and is cognitively easier for the respondents than the open-ended format. Econometric models are used to identify key drivers of the stated WTP, such as income, education, or environmental attitudes.

4.2.2. Choice experiment

CE surveys present respondents with repeated choices between alternatives, each described by multiple attributes (e.g. number of species, reduction in re-listed species, cost); see e.g. Boeri et al. [11]; Jobstovogt et al. [43]. From respondents' choices, the analyst can estimate an underlying utility function and the WTP for different levels of each of the attributes. In this respect a CE survey gives more information than a CV survey.

Boyd and Krupnick [12] suggested that attributes should be thought of as endpoints that directly affect the utility. Schultz et al. [73] suggested that attributes should meet several criteria: they should be measurable (endpoints are quantifiable), interpretable (endpoints are understood by respondents), applicable (attributes are relevant for the good or project in question and the endpoints must be linked to specific effects, such as changes in ecosystem services over which respondents have preferences), and comprehensive (all relevant endpoints are described in the survey). Thus, values associated with e.g., forest biodiversity, may be described using attributes of species richness [40].

CE face similar challenges as CV, with added complexity from many choice sets or attributes. Excessive complexity can lower data quality, as respondents may answer carelessly or rely on simplified rules.

4.3. The production function method

The environment is crucial in supporting the production of goods and services sold in markets. An economic production function describes the relationship between production factors (input) and output of the production. The production function (PFM) method focuses on economic productivity and how it increases with environmental quality and is based on production and cost data [3,4]. The PFM is founded on the concept that the value of non-marketed environmental inputs can be assessed by their contribution to the value of the final product that is sold. If there is a market price for the produced good it is straightforward to estimate the marginal value of the non-marketed input by assessing its impact on the output's value [38]. To conduct a more thorough welfare assessment, one could also examine changes in the marginal value of marketed inputs within the production function. An improvement in environmental quality will affect the marginal cost of the output. If marginal cost decreases and increases consumer- and producer surplus, this change can be used to infer the value of non-marketed environmental input. The production function approach is often applied to

² Incentive compatibility means that respondents have incentives to tell their true and fully preferences.

model restoration processes and assess their economic implications (see e.g. [61]).

5. Results and discussion of critical aspects of valuation methods

5.1. Overview of valuation studies in Europe

In Table A1 in the appendix, we list all the scientific articles that qualified to be included in the literature review. In Table 1 we summarize the main characteristics of the studies.

A large majority of the studies use stated preferences, with more than 80 % of the studies using either CVM or CE. Only 5 % have used HPM and PFM, respectively. Since many studies (71 %) focus on recreational values, the TCM has been used in 17 % of the studies. Studies about biodiversity are also common (57 %), while only very few studies have investigated health related aspects such as noise reduction or air quality. Moreover, 40 % of the studies focus on visitors to the NbS; these could be visitors to an urban park, anglers beside a river, or bird watchers visiting a forest. Even many of the stated preference surveys focus primarily on the direct use values of NbS. Rather naturally, many stated preference studies focus on citizens living close to the NbS (36 %), while there is a smaller share of studies (24 %) that include a nationwide sample of citizens.

5.2. What values are we measuring and what should we measure?

Table 2 summarizes which values can be measured by the non-market valuation methods that we review in this paper.

Note that only SP methods can measure non-use values. Moreover, non-use values are especially relevant for biodiversity; Wattage and Mardle [83] found that 45 % of the total value for wetland conservation in Sri Lanka was non-use values, and Marre et al. [58] found that the share of non-use values was 25–40 % for protecting the coral reef ecosystem. In contrast, Revealed Preference (RP) and Production Function (PF) methods focus on use values and cannot assess values for new goods or future improvements or include any non-use values in their estimations.

However, in practice, most SP studies focus on citizens and specific non-market aspects; for example, leaving out the effects of provisioning services on agricultural productivity. Moreover, the choice of population in SP studies affects the scope of the values captured. For example, if only citizens from one country are surveyed, values from people in other regions are excluded, even if they benefit from the NbS. Similarly, small but significant user groups (e.g., local communities or firms) may be underrepresented with general sampling.

RP methods are limited in identifying the value of specific characteristics of an NbS. For example, a travel cost study of a single nature reserve captures the total recreational value, but not which characteristics of the nature reserve determine this value. To estimate this, we would need a more advanced travel cost study where people choose between a set of nature reserves, and a variation of the characteristics of the nature reserves that allows us to identify the relevance of individual characteristics of the nature reserve, e.g., the level of biodiversity.

Each method also differs in whose values are included. Hedonic pricing only captures the preferences of residents; travel costs include visitors. PF methods rely on data from specific sectors.

It can be tempting to use individual valuation studies to say something about the values of ecosystem services in general. This is not advisable. Most studies provide partial values. Aggregating such values across several NbS would not be appropriate. For example, someone willing to pay 1 % of their income to protect one park won't necessarily be willing to pay 10 % for ten parks.

Relying only on RP methods will likely underestimate the value of biodiversity, as these omit non-use values. SP methods are the only way to capture such values, though even these raise questions. For example,

should we include warm-glow or moral satisfaction effects in policy decisions? Some scholars argue these are context-dependent and may reflect social pressure rather than intrinsic value (e.g., [28]), while others argue they should still be counted [49].

Finally, deciding whose values to include in a valuation depends on the decision-making context. This includes citizens, experts, or policy-makers. The valuation methods can, to some extent, be used to inform the decision-maker about who benefits. There is a sizeable literature on distance-decay [39], in particular on use-values. The basic idea is that WTP declines with distance from the NbS, and by using distance as an explanatory variable, one can identify the cutoff at which WTP is zero. This would then inform us about who is benefiting from the NbS. However, many values, in particular non-use values, might not display distance decay. For example, the extinction of major species could have a global significance, and massive upscaling of an NbS in a country or a continent could also have global impacts that are not a function of the distance to the NbS.

5.2.1. Critical aspects of SP methods

As demonstrated by our meta-analysis, the vast majority of studies rely on stated preference methods, with over 80 % employing either contingent valuation (CVM) or choice experiments (CE). While stated preference methods remain the only available approach for capturing non-use values, their application raises several well-documented concerns that need to be discussed. A key concern in SP studies is whether individuals behave in surveys as they would in real-life situations. Hypothetical bias arises when respondents misrepresent their willingness to pay (WTP) in hypothetical settings. i.e. that they are willing to pay more in a non-binding survey situation than what they would pay in a real life. Studies show that hypothetical bias is a concern [54,60,67]. A meta-study by Penn and Hu [67] found that hypothetical WTP was on average 2.3 times higher than real WTP (median 1.39). This bias was larger for public goods. However, not all studies find such biases (e.g., [19,45]). To address hypothetical bias, mitigation techniques have been developed. There is no consensus on which of the techniques is the best, and they can be combined in the same study [55]. Mitigation techniques include cheap-talk scripts, certainty questions, consequential scripts, time-to-think protocols, and oath scripts. All but the certainty-question are ex-ante techniques, meaning that they occur before the main SP question(s) in a survey. Penn and Hu [67] analysed the impact of different methods and techniques for mitigating hypothetical bias. They found that choice experiments, cheap talk-, and consequential scripts, and certainty follow-up questions, all significantly reduced hypothetical bias. For example, follow-up questions reduced hypothetical bias by 73–100 %, while ex-ante scripts had a smaller impact. In the best-practice recommendations by Johnston et al. [46], the recommended ex-ante approach is a consequential survey with a binding payment.

It is essential to distinguish between goods with negligible and goods with sizeable non-use values, such as biodiversity [58,83]. There are notable challenges in measuring non-use values through hypothetical surveys. This does not imply that non-use values should not be measured, but rather that it is inherently difficult. Non-use values are found to be driven by e.g. warm-glow motivations [1].

Another issue is scope insensitivity: when WTP does not increase with the scale of environmental change. Kahneman and Knetsch [47] argue that this stems from moral satisfaction rather than economic reasoning. In a study, WTP to prevent fish population decline in all Ontario lakes was only slightly higher than for a small area of the province. Subsequent studies (e.g., [20,29]) and meta-analyses (e.g. [44, 53,71]) report mixed findings: some confirm scope insensitivity, others find positive or even negative scope effects. Explanations include warm-glow motivations [62], poor survey design or limited information [20], and framing effects [5,65]. The latter shows that absolute measures (e.g. hectares) yield stronger scope sensitivity than relative ones.

Table 1
Main characteristics of valuation studies on biodiversity and NbS in Europe.

Method	Environment		Population		ESS		
CVM	36 %	Marine	17 %	Citizens (local)	36 %	Recreation	71 %
CE	45 %	Cropland	5 %	Citizens (national)	24 %	Biodiversity	57 %
TCM	17 %	Forest	29 %	Visitors	40 %	Provisioning	12 %
HPM	5 %	Grassland	12 %			Noise reduction.	2 %
PFM	5 %	Urban	24 %	Type		Air quality	5 %
		Rivers & lakes	14 %	Manage	90 %	Aesthetics	12 %
				Protect	19 %	Climate reg.	5 %
				Restore	29 %	Supporting	10 %

Table 2
Overview of values and methods for measurement.

Ecosystem services	Values	Example good	RP	SP	PF
Provisioning services	Direct use	Nature reserve, recreation	Travel cost	Yes	No
		Food production	No	Yes	Yes
	Indirect use	Health effects	Hedonic	Yes	No
Regulating and maintenance services	Direct use	Health effects	Hedonic	Yes	No
	Indirect use	Human existence value	No	Yes	No
Cultural services	Non-use values	Existence value	No	Yes	No

5.2.2. Critical aspects of RP methods

As shown by our meta-analysis, RP methods are less commonly used to value biodiversity than SP methods. RP methods require well-functioning markets to estimate non-market values, which may not always be possible for biodiversity. In addition, non-experimental data often come with econometric challenges related to identification, such as endogeneity and omitted variables. At the same time, these methods do not suffer from hypothetical bias.

5.2.2.1. *Travel cost.* If travel itself is enjoyable (e.g., scenic driving), one of the key assumptions that travel and time costs act as a proxy for the price of accessing the site is weakened. This means that the travel costs do not only reflect the value of accessing the site, which potentially inflates value estimates. Second, if trips serve multiple purposes (e.g., combining recreation with errands), attributing all costs to recreation can overstate the site’s value. Lastly, variation in trip length is a challenge as travel costs for short and long trips cannot be simply aggregated [52]. Addressing these issues is essential for accurately estimating the value of environmental resources.

5.2.2.2. *Hedonic pricing.* HPM faces several critical challenges. First, the method assumes perfect competition and that markets are in equilibrium, which is often unrealistic due to time lags or information asymmetries. It is unlikely that house buyers and sellers have perfect information, in particular regarding environmental attributes such as air quality and proximity to green space. Moreover, buyers and sellers are assumed to have the freedom to enter and exit the market, but without market power to affect the price of the property significantly. Finally, all levels of the characteristics of the properties should be available, so buyers can move to their preferred option. Second, model misspecification can lead to biased welfare estimates. Omitting relevant variables (e.g., school quality) or using the wrong function form (e.g., linear vs. non-linear) can bias estimates. There is also identification challenges associated with the application of the two-step procedure [32]. Finally, multicollinearity is a common issue due to the strong correlations between explanatory variables, such as neighbourhood

characteristics, school quality, and environmental attributes. High multicollinearity can make it difficult to determine the individual contribution of each variable to property prices, inflating standard errors, and reducing the statistical reliability of the estimated coefficients. These limitations highlight the need for careful model specification, data collection, and statistical techniques to improve the reliability of HPM in valuing environmental goods.

5.2.3. Critical aspects of the PFM

Only 5 % of the studies in our meta-analysis have used PFM. To value the environment as an input, one needs to have a deep knowledge of the relationship between various inputs and outputs in the environment. The complexity of ecosystems and lack of knowledge of the inherent complex interrelations are some of the challenges in using the PFM for valuing ecosystem services. Another related challenge is the problem of double-counting, which occurs if both the intermediate ecosystem functions and the final ecosystem services are estimated separately and aggregated in assessing the final value of an ecosystem service [3,7,36].³

6. Discussion of critical aspects of the valuation of NbS

We have so far identified the existing literature on non-market valuation of NbS and biodiversity, and have critically reviewed the methods employed in these studies. We now turn to a discussion of a few important additional aspects that are broadly applicable to the valuation of NbS and biodiversity, irrespective of the valuation method employed, namely complexity and uncertainty.

6.1. Complexity and uninformed citizens

Biodiversity is inherently complex, making it unlikely that citizens, firms, or even policymakers fully understand its implications. This raises the question: can public preferences reliably inform policy? Some might argue we should not make policy decisions based on individual preferences under such circumstances. However, policy makers do not have perfect information, and experts may differ from the general population not only in their expertise but also in other important aspects, such as income and preferences, which could make them less representative of the citizens [17,31].

Suppose that citizen preferences matter; then there are several aspects to consider if citizens are uninformed. 1. Decision utility versus experienced utility [48]. Decision utility reflects the perceived satisfaction or benefits that decision-makers believe they derive from their choice. All the methods we covered so far are based on decision utility. Experienced utility refers to the satisfaction that people experience after making a choice and utilizing the good. A small body of research highlights the potential of using experienced utility to value non-market

³ Double counting is a well-known term in economics that originally was used to refer to the erroneous practice of aggregating the value of a nation’s goods and services. The problem arises when both the intermediate and the final good are aggregated and misses that the final good includes the value of the intermediate good.

goods; see, e.g., Welsch [85,86], Luechinger [56], and Ferreira and Moro [35]. This approach involves using self-reported subjective well-being as a proxy for individual utility, allowing researchers to compute the marginal rate of substitution between income and non-marketed goods. From this, it is possible to infer the monetary value of non-marketed goods, offering a more experience-based measure of their contribution to welfare. A challenge with using subjective well-being responses is that they may be subject to biases common in survey methods, such as social desirability bias (see, e.g., [9,18]).

2. Focus on certain aspects. Because of the complexity, behaviour and even policy, might focus on certain aspects of the problem; for example, a disproportional focus on direct use values of ecosystems, or certain types of species, such as iconic species.

How does complexity affect valuation methods? Revealed preference methods rely on informed consumers; a lack of information distorts the valuation benefits of biodiversity. SP method allows researchers to provide information in the survey, helping respondents make more informed choices. This is not as simple as it sounds. Task complexity in SP studies can affect the extent of inconsistent choices, the decision rules adopted by the respondents, and the welfare estimates (see, e.g., [27, 74]). The effects of some changes may be challenging to express in a survey using terms and language that are easily understood by respondents. In addition, some changes are complex and multidimensional and may provide only a limited picture of reality [63]. In SP, ways to improve the communication of complex scenarios have been explored. For example, Tagliaferro et al. [76] conducted a landscape analysis in a three-dimensional space to provide ecologically meaningful quantitative landscape indicators to respondents in a study on landscape valuation in Italy. Another development is the use of virtual reality since this would provide respondents with more freedom to explore different scenarios and to understand what would happen and how it would look [15]. For example, Bateman et al. [6] used a virtual reality world in which respondents can fly around and explore the area, and Fiore et al. [37] used a virtual reality world where forest fires are simulated. However, it is far from clear that this would resolve all issues with complexity.

In summary, while it is hard to neglect the advantages of the stated preference methods to inform uninformed respondents, it does still come with its problems.

6.2. Uncertainty

Uncertainty is a central challenge in valuing biodiversity. Climate change, pandemics, and food insecurity are examples of risks that can cause catastrophic losses with loss of human lives. The valuation of such impacts can be quantified using the Value of a Statistical life (VSL); see, e.g. Viscusi and Aldy [82]. This is a measure of the value of reductions in mortality risks, i.e., how much individuals are willing to pay for small reductions in the probability of death. VSL can be estimated with hedonic wage methods [82] and with stated preference methods [51].

Quantifying these risks is complex and challenging. One could argue for a precautionary approach for situations of potentially unlimited downside exposure [84]. However, what is less studied and understood are the economic and financial risks associated with biodiversity loss. Understanding these risks is particularly important in a complex system, where there could be threshold effects and unexpected outcomes [69].

A key concept here is option value: the value of maintaining an option. Two aspects of ecosystems make option values important. The first is that future benefits may be unknown or uncertain. This implies a value of protecting the ecosystem because it might have value in the future. The second is that degradation or destruction of ecosystems can be irreversible or costly to restore. Option value is thus an additional value of protecting and restoring ecosystems. The option value would depend on what we think the unknown/uncertain benefits are and what the costs of restoring ecosystems are (the degree of irreversibility). The EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 [33] reflects this thinking, emphasizing

ecosystem protection as a way to build resilience to future threats such as climate change and disease outbreaks. Ultimately, accounting for uncertainty and option value strengthens the economic case for investing in Nature-based Solutions (NbS). These investments may yield benefits that could help buffer society against long-term systemic risks.

7. Conclusions

A barrier to recognizing NbS for biodiversity loss is limited evidence of its effectiveness and economic value [10]. The complexity, various sources of values, and scale across space and time of NbS mean many challenges. To acknowledge the complexity of biodiversity and ecosystems is important not only for assessing the values of NbS but also when communicating about its role and what values it provides. This can be important both for policy support but also for funding. If investors do not understand the role of NbS, and what values it provides, they will make other choices. NbS can often be a substitute to grey infrastructure with engineering-based solutions, e.g. coastal wetlands can be an alternative to concrete sea defence walls.⁴ It's therefore important to investigate how NbS compares to "engineering solutions" and man-made structures.

Moreover, we show that NbS provides many non-use values like cultural, spiritual, and existence values. Although direct-use values are often of primary concern, based on our review, we believe there is a clear risk of disregarding both indirect-use values and non-use values. While this could be a lower bound of the actual benefits, important values might be lost. Furthermore, since NbS often provides a wide array of values, values that are more difficult to measure and monetize might be left out.

Finally, given the complexities of the ecosystem, the risks of catastrophic and unexpected outcomes with consequences for the whole economy are important. The valuation literature rarely focuses on the broader picture, despite non-negligible risks of catastrophic outcomes for ecosystems and humans. A narrow focus on individual studies of specific NbS or ecosystem services, as observed in much of the reviewed literature, entails a significant risk of overlooking broader systemic outcomes.

Comprehensive frameworks are needed to integrate various valuation methods and capture the full benefits of NbS. When comparing biodiversity loss to other major global challenges, such as climate change, the scientific community has established clearer links between emissions levels, global warming, and their impacts on human welfare, often measured by Gross Domestic Product (GDP). This clarity enables the assessment of welfare effects across various business scenarios, differing in their mitigation ambitions, over time. In contrast, a similarly rigorous framework for biodiversity is yet to be developed. This poses a significant challenge, as biodiversity loss cannot be addressed through a single, dominant mechanism like reducing global CO₂ emissions. Moreover, research on biodiversity often lacks a strong focus on effectively integrating the economic valuation of nature-based solutions (NbS) into policymaking and investment decisions. Such integration is essential to fully realize and protect the wide-ranging benefits that NbS offers.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Fredrik Carlsson: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Mitesh Kataria:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original

⁴ Vicarelli et al., [81] examined 87 published scientific studies about 402 NbS sites. They compared the cost-effectiveness of the NbS solutions with engineering-based solutions and found that 65 % of these studies concluded that NbS are always more effective in attenuating hazards compared to engineering-based solutions and 26 % found that NbS are partially more effective.

draft, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Elina Lampi:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

Elina Lampi reports financial support was provided by European Union. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix

Table A1
List of studies.

Reference	Country	Method	Type of environment	Type of ESS	Target population	Type of NbS
Chae et al. [94]	U.K.	TCM	Marine	Recreation	Visitors	Manage
Alessandro et al. [88]	Italy	TCM	Forest	Recreation	Visitors	Manage
Latinopoulos et al. [110]	Greece	CVM	Marine	Biodiversity	Citizens (local)	Manage
Getzner et al. [103]	Croatia	CVM	Marine	Biodiversity, Recreation	Visitors	Manage
Juutinen et al. [109]	Finland	CE	Forest	Biodiversity, Recreation	Visitors	Manage
Czajkowski et al. [99]	Poland	CE	Forest	Biodiversity	Citizens (national)	Manage, protect
Black et al. [92]	U.K.	CVM	Grassland	Biodiversity, Recreation	Visitors	Manage, protect
Boeri et al. [11]	U.K.	CE	Coast	Biodiversity, Recreation, Cultural	Citizens (national)	Restore
Crespo-Cebada et al. [98]	Spain	CE	Forest, River	Biodiversity, Recreation	Visitors	Manage, restore
Ratzke [70]	Germany	HPM	Urban	Biodiversity	Citizens (local)	Manage, protect
Getzner & Švajda [102]	Slovakia	CVM	Forest	Recreation	Visitor	Manage
Jobstvogt [43]	Scotland	CE	Marine	Provisioning, Biodiversity	Citizens (national)	Manage, protect
Tonin [119]	Italy	CVM	Marine	Biodiversity	Citizens (national)	Manage, restore
Tonin [118]	Italy	CVM	Marine	Biodiversity	Citizens (national)	Manage, restore
Rousseau & Fuertes [116]	Netherlands	CE, TCM	Rivers & lakes	Recreation	Visitors	Manage
Getzner [101]	Poland	CVM	Forest	Biodiversity, Recreation	Visitors	Manage
Grazhdani [105]	Albania, Greece, Macedonia	CVM, TCM	Rives & lakes	Recreation	Visitors	Manage
Tonin [77]	Italy	CVM	Marine	Biodiversity, Recreation	Citizens (national)	Manage, protect, restore
Tyrväinen, L. [121]	Finland	CVM	Urban	Recreation	Citizens (local)	Manage
Grilli et al. [106]	Ireland, U.K.	TCM	Rivers & lakes	Recreation	Visitors	Manage
Simões [117]	Portugal	CE, TCM	Forest	Recreation	Visitors	Manage, protect
Collins [97]	U.K.	CE	Urban	Biodiversity	Visitors	Manage
Brandolini [93]	Italy	CVM	Rivers & lakes	Recreation	Visitors	Manage
Riepe et al. [115]	Germany, France, Norway, Sweden	CE	Rivers & lakes	Biodiversity, Provisioning, Recreation	Citizens (national)	Manage, restore
Meyerhoff et al. [113]	Germany	CE	Rivers & lakes	Biodiversity, Recreation	Visitors	Manage
Meyerhoff et al. [114]	Germany	CE	Forest	Biodiversity	Citizens (local)	Manage
Varela [122]	Belgium, Germany	CE	Crop, Forest, Grassland	Biodiversity	Citizens (local)	Manage, restore
Horne [40]	Finland	CE	Forest	Biodiversity, Recreation	Visitors	Manage
Tyrväinen & Miettinen [80]	Finland	HPM	Urban	Biodiversity, Recreation, Noise reduction, Air quality, Aesthetics	Citizens (local)	Manage

(continued on next page)

Table A1 (continued)

Reference	Country	Method	Type of environment	Type of ESS	Target population	Type of NbS
Willis & Benson [123]	U.K.	TCM	Forest, Grassland	Recreation	Citizens (local)	Manage
Christie & Rayment [96]	U.K.	CE	Grassland, Inland wetland, Coastal	Provisioning, supporting, climate regulation, flood regulation, recreation, biodiversity, cultural	Citizens (national)	Manage, protect
Chen et al. [95]	Belgium	CVM	Grassland	Regulating, supporting, flood regulation, recreation	Citizens (national)	Restore
Mell et al. [112]	U.K.	CVM	Urban	Aesthetics, air quality	Citizens (local)	Manage
Birol et al. [90]	Poland	CE	Wetland	Flood regulation, biodiversity, recreation	Citizens (local)	Manage
Bishop [91]	U.K.	CVM	Urban	Recreation	Visitors	Manage
Hanley & Knight [108]	U.K.	CVM	Urban	Biodiversity, Recreation, Aesthetics	Citizens (local)	Protect
Bertram et al. [89]	Germany	CE	Urban	Biodiversity, Recreation	Citizens (local)	Manage
Giergiczny & Kronenberg [104]	Poland	CE	Urban	Local climate regulation, aesthetics	Citizens (local)	Manage, restore
Hampson et al. [107]	U.K.	CE	Rivers & lakes	Biodiversity, Recreation	Citizens (local)	Manage, restore
Tu et al. [120]	France	CE	Urban	Recreation, Aesthetics	Citizens (local)	Manage
Masiero et al. [111]	Italy	PFM	Forest	Provisioning, supporting, biodiversity, recreation, aesthetics	Citizens (national)	Manage, restore
Faure et al. [100]	France	PFM	Crop	Provisioning, supporting	Citizens (local)	Restore
Number of articles	42					

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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